

ISic4417

Epitaph for [-?-], child of Gerontios

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

sandstone

Object

plinth

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Autopsy

Metcalfe 2016 visited site

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Abacaenum

Place of origin (modern)

near Tripi

Provenance

Tomb 80 of the necropolis in contrada Cardusa , where it remains in situ

Coordinates

38.065190, 15.114380

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Tripi, Necropoli di Abakainon

Physical Description

Plinth (support for a stele) with mouldings top and bottom, of the local sandstone; the upper part of the plinth is heavily damaged, with all of the left corner missing and the upper right. The plinth is the left one of a pair mounted on a single base, classified as an epitymbion of type C.

Dimensions

Height 30 cm

Width 48 cm

Depth 63 cm

Layout

Remains of two lines of Greek letters, apparently centred on the face of the plinth; the second line sits directly above the lower moulding

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Simple, widely spaced letters. Omega is wide and open, with horizontal tails; rho has a large, closed eye; omicron is small and mid-line; nu is regular and with both verticals full length

Letter heights:

Line 1-2: 30 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: Not recorded mm

Text

1. [---]ω[---]

2. [Γ]ἔρόντιου

Apparatus

text based upon photographs

Sofia 2018: [---]ωι[---]; the final vertical could either be iota or the first stroke of a nu; it is uncertain if any letters may have been lost beyond this.

Sofia 2018: [---] ροντιου

Translation (en)

[?] (child) of Gerontios

Commentary

Interpretation of this fragmentary text is context dependent. The text/plinth forms a pair with the adjoining plinth ISic4418 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic4418>]. On that second plinth, the genitive .εροντιου is legible in the second line, and the trace of a vertical stroke is visible before the first epsilon, at some distance. The only attested Greek name compatible with this is Γερόντιος [http://clas-igpn2.classics.ox.ac.uk/cgi-bin/igpn_search.cgi?name=%CE%93%CE%B5%CF%81%CF%8C%CE%BD%CF%84%CE%B9%CE%BF%CF%82], which is known in later Roman times at Catania (ISic3199 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic3199>]) and Syracuse (Orsi 1896 [<https://www.zotero.org/groups/isicily/items/H73GNMU6>]: 31 no.318). Comparison with other examples of paired monuments in this necropolis, particularly ISic4415 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic4415>] / ISic4416 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic4416>], shows that these monuments can record siblings. It is therefore all but certain that we can restore the name Γερόντιος here in line 2, and that these two plinths also record siblings. In a few cases, including ISic4415/ISic4416, the first name is presented in the nominative, and therefore it is unsafe to assume that what may well be the final letter of line 1 is an iota; a nu, giving a nominative ending in -ων would be entirely possible and compatible with the state of the stone (compare ISic4416).

Digital identifiers:

URI <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic4417>

DOI [10.5281/zenodo.4022728](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4022728)

Bibliography

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At 113 and 166 tav.XXXIVa-b

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Cardusa a Tripi. Terme Vigliatore (ME). At 113 fig.115

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